

PECULIARITIES OF STUDYING ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN DERIVATIONAL ELEMENTS THROUGH MEDIA TEXTS

Merganova Sh.A.

Shevtsova O.V.

Introduction

Word-formation has always been a significant area of study for linguists. Its influence and effect spread to various fields of language, including advertisements. One of the most significant types of word-formation is derivation. According to Vinogradov V.V., the process of creating new words or new meanings with the help of prefix or suffix is called derivation (1960). This phenomenon in particular has been utilized as a tool for foregrounding in media texts. Its use varies from traditional forms to forms, which result in language deviations. Its role in attracting people’s attention and persuading them to purchase something has been closely studied and developed throughout the history of linguistics.

However, not many researches were conducted on the allomorphic features in application of derivational elements between two languages, particularly English and Russian. It can be stated that the outcome of this study can potentially shed a light on the similarities and differences between English and Russian media texts and their unique use of derivational elements. Hence, this paper addresses the peculiarities of derivatives in English and Russian languages, and analyzes them from various angles.

Literature review

The literature review further supports the idea that little to no research has been done to analyze the difference in use of derivation in English and Russian languages. Nevertheless, these fields of study were extensively dissected separately. For example, it is observed that there are many instances of derivation being used in Russian advertisement. They could be taken from either Russian language or they could come from any different language. Nowadays, the popularity of international derivational elements can be observed. It is believed that they manage to draw more attention from younger audience, rather than native morphemes (Ratsiburskaya, 2014).

However, they are still expected to be adapted into the Russian language. Thus, in media texts, mostly the common foreign derivational elements are implemented. In support of this statement, M.Kalinina comes to the conclusion that the context and familiarity of the word plays an essential role in acceptance of the advertisements.

With the help of derivational elements such as “lux” which is altered to “люксовый”, she points out the positive effect from using well-known and popular foreign derivational elements (2017). Similarly, prefixes such as “псевдо-, супер-, ультра-, экс-” have a great significance in Russian word-formation due to their deep-rooted adaptation into Russian lexicon (Potapova, 2010).

On the other hand, there is quite a noticeable distinction in use of the derivation in English advertisements. The English media texts are peculiar with the freedom and flexibility of the context. The main focus of them is usually on gaining the sympathy of wider demographic. N.Batelino, M.Trebusq and Y.Velazquez state that specifically verbs with addition of derivational elements tend to get wider meaning and set of actions, rather than becoming a new word (2015). In addition, various slangs, culturally-specific terms also become a derivative (Zaytseva, 2012). For example, the word “revolution” is changed to “revolutionize” and used in the advertisements in the meaning of drastically improving something. Many slang words are used as derivational elements to specifically make the text more interesting and engaging (Seres, 2021).

All these findings imply that the main difference between Russian and English language derivation in advertisement is their approach to context. However, no exact research has been conducted to further prove or refute this point. Thus, this paper intends to compare various advertisements and find out the peculiarities of using derivational elements in media text in both languages.

Research data and process

The research was carried out with the help of comparative and cross-cultural methods. As the examples that were gathered were quite unique, comparative method was the most suited one to showcase the similarities and differences in English and Russian derivation. Comparative method is often used by linguists to analyze languages synchronically and diachronically (Joseph & Janda, 2003). Besides, the frequency of the parts of speech where derivational elements were added were also analyzed with the means of comparative method. When it comes to cross-cultural method, it was applied, because the nature of culture can greatly affect the language and its structure. Comparative study lets linguists and culturologists to perceive the commonalties between various cultures (Ember, 2009). This method allows to objectively see the allomorphic features of compared languages.

To conduct this study, advertisement texts in Russian and English were collected. The words containing derivation were selected and thoroughly analyzed.

How derivation created was and what kind of message it had were the main questions on which this research relied. The aforementioned methods were selected, because they seemed to be the most appropriate and produced an accurate outcome.

The use of derivation in Russian and English

Derivational elements are added to the word that conveys the main meaning of the slogan in both Russian and English languages. They contain the twist of the advertisements which serves as a tool for foregrounding.

“No One Outpizzas the Hut”

“Не тормози — сникерсни”

The different derivational elements were added to the words to create a new meaning of verb, which is related to the sold item. Pizza Hut and Snickers used their respective food and gave it a broader semantic depth by making their company name into verb.

Derivational elements and parts of speech

In English, the added derivational element mainly changes the word into verb or is added to verb to create a certain action or new term which persuades the consumer to get interested in the product.

“How Doers Get More Done”

Home Depot used this slogan and the word “Doer” which is taken from the verb “do” to unite all people of various skill level. The change of verb into noun was done by adding the suffix “er”.

On the other hand, in Russian languages, derivational elements are mostly added to the noun or the noun word is created to convey the selling point.

“Полный Ахе-Эффект”

Here the prefix “Ахе” is taken from the name of the product Axe to signify how their deodorants change other people’s perception for good. “Ахе” in this sentence serves as a prefix which carries semantic significance.

Conclusion

After researching about derivational elements, it is prominent that there is a vast difference between Russian and English implementation. The tone varies according to the culture as well. This data can be used by other linguists to study the peculiarities of English and Russian in publicistic style. It can also be very beneficial for teachers to showcase the importance of culture in learning the language. However, it should be noted that this research is not very deep, considering the number of examples taken for analysis. It could be extended to get even more information regarding the

comparison, or the new study can be conducted by comparing one more language with English and Russian.

References:

1. Балакин С. (2014). *Понятие деривационного потенциала языковой и концептуальной систем*. Вестник Ленинградского государственного университета им. А. С. Пушкина. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ponyatie-derivatsionnogo-potentsiala-yazykovoy-i-kontseptualnoy-sistem>
2. Виноградов В., Истрина Е., Бархударов С. (1960). *Грамматика русского языка*. Издательство Академии наук СССР.
3. Зайцева Л. (2012). *Английский язык в рекламе*. Издательство «Флинта».
4. Калинина М. (2017). *Выявление деривационных возможностей иноязычной лексики в русском языке*. Известия Волгоградского государственного педагогического университета. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-voprosu-o-derivatsionnyh-vozmozhnostyah-inoyazychnoy-leksiki-v-russkom-yazyke-na-primere-gallitsizmov>
5. Потапова Г. (2010). *Именная префиксация как активный деривационный процесс словообразования современного русского языка*. Преподаватель XXI век.
6. Рацибурская Л. (2014). *Проявление интернационализации в современном медийном словотворчестве*. Филология и культура. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/proyavlenie-internatsionalizatsii-v-sovremennom-mediynom-slovotvorchestve#:~:text=%D0%98%D0%BD%D1%82%D0%B5%D1%80%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%86%D0%B8%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%B0%D0%BB%D0%B8%D0%B7%D0%B0%D1%86%D0%B8%D1%8F%20%D0%B2>
7. Щербакова Н., Досанова А. (2014). *Использование семантической деривации в современном пространстве рекламы (на примере номинаций биологически активных добавок)*. Вестник Сибирского института бизнеса и информационных технологий. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ispolzovanie-semanticheskoy-derivatsii-v-sovremennom-prostranstve-reklamy-na-primere-nominatsiy-biologicheski-aktivnyh-dobavok>
8. Battellino N., Trebucq M., & Velázquez Y. (2015). *Morphological Awareness: The Impact of Derivation on the English Lexicon*. III ELT Conference at UNVM: Rethinking English Language Teaching.
9. Ember C., & Ember M. (2009). *Cross-cultural Research Methods*. A Division of Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, Inc.
10. Joseph B., & Janda R. (2003). *The Handbook of Historical Linguistics*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
11. Seres N. (2021). *Types of Word Formation of Colloquial Vocabulary in British and American Advertisements*. Ferenc Rakoczi II Transcarpathian Hungarian College of Higher Education Department of Philology.